

microfibril associated protein 4 (MFAP4) : Machine learning discoveries of 2^{nd} order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : MFAP4 is an extracellular matrix protein belonging to the family of proteoglycans, which are involved in intercellular interactions ,cell adhesion and the assembly and/or maintenance of elastic fibres. It has been observed in higher levels in lungs and vasculature. Further, it has been known to be implicated in cardiovascular disease, experimental allergic asthma, stenosis, osteoarthritis, hepatic fibrosis and pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma. However, its role in meningiomas has not yet been determined completely. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interations with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2^{nd} order combinations of MFAP4, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

*ML dicoveries of MFAP4 synergy in Meningiomas

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Keywords: MFAP4, Meningioma, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angiomatic, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Württemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagioccephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecortius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation.

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. microfibril associated protein 4 (MFAP4)

MFAP 4 is a part of proteoglycans, which are proteins that are heavily glycosylated. These are involved in intercellular interactions, cell adhesion, and the assembly and/or maintenance of elastic fibres. Elastic fibers (or yellow fibers) are components of the extracellular matrix composed of bundles of proteins like elastin, elanin and oxytalan.

Kobayashi et al. [13] reported the biochemical characterization of a newly identified microfibril-associated protein of 36-kDa (36-kDa MAP) from bovine aorta. They acquired a pure form of 36-kDa MAP, using Ca^{2+} -dependent affinity chromatography on an isoquinolinesulfonamide derivative (CKA-1303)-coupled Sepharose. Further, they found that MAP bound to Ca^{2+} . They determined a partial amino acid sequence of 36-kDa MAP and resemblance to fibrinogen-related proteins of sea cucumber, cytotactin and tenascin which are substrate-adhesion proteins made at critical stages of

histogenesis, was found.

Smith-Magenis syndrome (SMS) is a clinically recognizable multiple congenital anomaly/mental retardation syndrome associated with deletion of chromosome 17p11.2. Zhao et al. [14] reported the identification of a novel gene encoding a human microfibril-associated glycoprotein (MFAP4), which was mapped to the SMS region. They observed that MFAP4 had a fibrinogen-like domain and shared a high level of sequence homology to a fragment of a bovine 36 kDa microfibril-associated glycoprotein. Further, its N-terminus of the protein bore an Arg-Gly-Asp sequence that served as the ligand motif for cell surface receptor integrin. These structural features of MFAP4 suggested that it was an extracellular matrix protein involved in cell adhesion or intercellular interactions. They also found that the MFAP4 locus was deleted in 30 of 31 SMS patients. Thus they thought of the requirement of investigation of this gene in the pathogenesis of SMS.

1.3. Roles of MFAP4 in different disease

Wulf-Johansson et al. [15] tried to identify tissues with high levels of MFAP4 mRNA and MFAP4 protein expression and further aimed to evaluate the significance of MFAP4 as a marker of **cardiovascular disease** (CVD) and to correlate MFAP4 with other known ECM markers, such as fibulin-1, osteopontin (OPN) and osteoprotegerin (OPG). qRT-PCR demonstrated that MFAP4 mRNA was more highly expressed in the heart, intestine and lung, than in other elastic tissues. Their immunohistochemical studies showed high levels of MFAP4 protein at sites rich in elastic fibers and within blood vessels in all tissues under consideration. Serum MFAP4 levels were observed to be significantly lower in patients with stable atherosclerotic disease than coronary artery calcification (CAC-negative) individuals. Their study suggested that serum MFAP4 varied in groups of patients with different cardiovascular conditions.

Pilecki et al. [16] investigated the role of MFAP4 in **experimental allergic asthma**, which is an extracellular matrix protein abundant in the lung. They observed that MFAP4 deficiency attenuated hallmarks of asthma, such as eotaxin production, eosinophilic inflammation, hyperresponsiveness and airway remodelling. In wild-type mice, they saw and increased serum MFAP4 after disease development and correlated with local eotaxin levels. Further, MFAP4 was expressed in human bronchial smooth muscle cells and its expression was found to be upregulated in asthmatic cells. Further, they established the mechanism in which MFAP4 interacted with integrin $\alpha v \beta 5$ and promoted asthmatic bronchial smooth muscle cell proliferation and CCL11 release dependent on phosphatidylinositol-3-kinase but not extracellular signal-regulated kinase pathway.

Arterial injury stimulates remodeling responses that, when excessive, lead to **stenosis**. These responses are influenced by integrin signaling in vascular smooth muscle cells (VSMCs). MFAP4 is an integrin ligand localized to extracellular matrix fibers in the vascular wall and Schlosser et al. [17] aimed to test the hypothesis that MFAP4 would enhance integrin-dependent VSMC activation. When they challenged with carotid artery ligation, MFAP4-deficient MFAP4^{-/-} mice exhibited delayed neointimal formation, accompanied by early reduction in the number of proliferating medial and neointimal cells, as well as infiltrating leukocytes. They observed that delayed neointimal formation was associated with decreased cross-sectional area of ligated

MFAP4^{-/-} carotid arteries that resulted in lumen narrowing 28 days after ligation, while MFAP4 blockade inhibited the formation of neointimal hyperplasia *ex vivo*. Further, they demonstrated that MFAP4 was a ligand for integrin $\alpha V\beta 3$ and mediated VSMC phosphorylation of focal adhesion kinase, migration, and proliferation *in vitro*. In addition, they showed that MFAP4 promoted monocyte chemotaxis in integrin $\alpha V\beta 3$ -dependent manner.

Although regeneration of human cartilage is inherently inefficient, age is an important risk factor for **osteoarthritis**. Reports have provided evidence that juvenile chondrocytes (from donors below 13 years of age) are more efficient at generating articular cartilage as compared to adult chondrocytes. To identify the cell-intrinsic differences between juvenile and adult cartilage, Taylor et al. [18] profiled global gene expression changes between a small cohort of human neonatal/juvenile and adult chondrocytes. Their studies identified and validated new factors enriched in juvenile chondrocytes as compared to adult chondrocytes including secreted extracellular matrix factors chordin-like 1 (CHRDL1) and MFAP4.

Even after eradication of viremic hepatitis C virus (HCV) with direct acting antivirals (DAAs), **hepatic fibrosis** remains a risk factor for hepatocarcinogenesis. After confirming the applicability of MFAP4 as a serum biomarker for the assessment of hepatic fibrosis, Mölleken et al. [19] assessed the usefulness of MFAP4 as a biomarker of liver fibrosis after HCV eliminating therapy with DAAs. MFAP4 serum levels were representative of the severity of hepatic fibrosis at baseline (BL) and correlated well with laboratory parameters, especially aspartate aminotransferase (AST) to platelet ratio index (APRI). They observed that laboratory parameters decreased from BL to end-of-therapy (EoT). MFAP4 serum levels were found to decrease from BL and end-of-therapy (EoT) to follow-up (FU) with high statistical significance. Their findings indicate that viral eradication resulted in reduced MFAP4 serum levels, presumably representing a decrease in hepatic fibrogenesis or fibrosis.

Late diagnosis of **pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma** (PDA) is one of the reasons of its low 5-year survival rate and it is due to its unspecific symptoms during the first stages of the disease and the lack of reliable serological markers. Since pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDA) shows an altered glycan expression, Guerrero et al. [20] focused on finding novel biomarkers, namely glycoproteins that express the tumor associated carbohydrate structure sialyl-Lewis x (sLe^x), which is described in PDA. They observed that MFAP4 showed a higher expression in PDA tissues compared with pancreatic control tissues. Further analysis of MFAP4 expression in PDA cell lines and their secretome, in combination with immunohistochemistry of pancreatic tissues, revealed that MFAP4 was not produced by PDA cells, but it was found in the pancreatic extracellular matrix. Through a glycoproteomic approach, they showed that the glycoprotein MFAP4 carried sLe^x in PDA tissues and not in control pancreatic tissues.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.4. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines has the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.5. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [21] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [22] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references citetd in Pujol et al. [22].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on

gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [23]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of forming the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [24], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [21] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [21]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [25], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")` • use `source("manuscript-2-2.R")` • use `source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R")`.

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings

provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. MFAP4 related synergies

Note - MFAP4 was found to be upregulated in Type B. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 392 2^{nd} order combinations of MFAP4 were recorded.

3.1.1. MFAP4 - individual genes

The following genes in combination with MFAP4 showed high rankings - heat shock protein family B (small) member 6 (HSPB6), prominin 1 (PROM1), elastin (ELN), LIM and cysteine rich domains 1 (LMCD1), solute carrier family 12 member 1 (SLC12A1), fibulin 1 (FBLN1), integrin subunit alpha 8 (ITGA8), ADCYAP receptor type I (ADCYAP1R1), semaphorin 5B (SEMA5B), sushi repeat containing protein X-linked (SRPX), proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin type 1 inhibitor (PCSK1N), solute carrier family 17 member 7 (SLC17A7), secreted frizzled related protein 4 (SFRP4), cadherin related 23 (CDH23), neuexin 2 (NRXN2), ST8 alpha-N-acetyl-neuraminide alpha-2,8-sialyltransferase 1 (ST8SIA1), natriuretic peptide receptor 3 (NPR3), podocalyxin like 2 (PODXL2), solute carrier family 30 member 3 (SLC30A3), proteoglycan 4 (PRG4), tripartite motif containing 67 (TRIM67), proteolipid protein 1 (PLP1), lysosomal associated membrane protein family member 5 (LAMP5), MBL associated serine protease 1 (MASP1), kinesin family member 1A (KIF1A), podocan like 1 (PODNL1), serpin family F member 1 (SERPINF1), C-type lectin domain containing 10A (CLEC10A), peripherin (PRPH), sodium voltage-gated channel alpha subunit 7 (SCN7A), tetratricopeptide repeat domain 29 (TTC29), thrombospondin 1 (THBS1), integrin subunit alpha 11 (ITGA11), dual oxidase 1 (DUOX1), luteinizing hormone/choriogonadotropin receptor (LHCGR), retinol binding protein 4 (RBP4), dual oxidase 2 (DUOX2), fibroblast growth factor 7 (FGF7), NKD inhibitor of WNT signaling pathway 1 (NKD1), reticulocalbin 3 (RCN3), neurexophilin 2 (NXPH2), RNA binding motif single stranded interacting protein 3 (RBMS3), BOC cell adhesion associated, oncogene regulated (BOC), cholinergic receptor nicotinic beta 3 subunit (CHRN3), dopamine receptor D2 (DRD2), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily A member 6 (KCNA6), phosphotyrosine interaction domain containing 1 (PID1), phosphodiesterase 1C (PDE1C), protein phosphatase 2 regulatory subunit Bbeta (PPP2R2B), S100 calcium binding protein B (S100B), collagen type XXVI alpha 1 chain (COL26A1), frizzled related protein (FRZB), C1q and TNF related 7 (C1QTNF7), Rho related BTB domain containing 3 (RHOBTB3), carbonic anhydrase 3 (CA3), sushi, von Willebrand factor type A, EGF and pentraxin domain containing 1 (SVEP1), heat shock protein family A (Hsp70) member 12A (HSPA12A), PDZ domain containing ring finger 4 (PDZRN4), transmembrane protein 130 (TMEM130), trans-golgi network vesicle protein 23 ho-

molog A (TVP23A), lactate dehydrogenase D (LDHD), proline rich transmembrane protein 2 (PRRT2), cytochrome P450 family 2 subfamily S member 1 (CYP2S1), 5'-nucleotidase domain containing 2 (NT5DC2), filamin A interacting protein 1 like (FILIP1L), RAB31, member RAS oncogene family (RAB31), nephronectin (NPNT), atonal bHLH transcription factor 8 (ATOH8), vesicle associated membrane protein 5 (VAMP5), armadillo repeat containing 4 / outer dynein arm docking complex subunit 2 (ARMC4 / ODAD2), coiled-coil domain containing 126 (CCDC126), G protein-coupled receptor 183 (GPR183), integrin subunit alpha M (ITGAM), G protein-coupled receptor 27 (GPR27), microtubule associated protein 6 (MAP6), mono-ADP ribosyl-hydrolase 2 (MACROD2), StAR related lipid transfer domain containing 5 (STARD5), interleukin 17D (IL17D), pseudopodium enriched atypical kinase 1 (PEAK1), heart development protein with EGF like domains 1 (HEG1), homeobox B2 (HOXB2), CD248 molecule (CD248), purinergic receptor P2Y14 (P2RY14), yippee like 2 (YPEL2), family with sequence similarity 131 member A (FAM131A), calcium binding protein 4 (CABP4), MEF2 activating motif and SAP domain containing transcriptional regulator (MAMSTR), frizzled class receptor 8 (FZD8), myozenin 1 (MYOZ1), phosphodiesterase 4D interacting protein (PDE4DIP), cysteine and serine rich nuclear protein 3 (CSRNP3), class II major histocompatibility complex transactivator (CIITA), serine rich and transmembrane domain containing 1 (SERTM1), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily E regulatory subunit 1 (KCNE1), NME/NM23 family member 9 (NME9), PLAG1 zinc finger (PLAG1), exostosin glycosyltransferase 1 (EXT1), biglycan (BGN), EPH receptor B3 (EPHB3), pyrroline-5-carboxylate reductase 1 (PYCR1), nebulin (NEB), family with sequence similarity 43 member B (FAM43B), adrenoceptor alpha 2C (ADRA2C), colony stimulating factor 1 (CSF1), fibronectin leucine rich transmembrane protein 2 (FLRT2), protein kinase cGMP-dependent 1 (PRKG1), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily Z member 1 (CYP4Z1), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily X member 1 (CYP4X1), reticulon 4 receptor like 2 (RTN4RL2), A-kinase anchoring protein 19 (C2orf88 / AKAP19), kelch repeat and BTB domain containing 12 (KBTBD12), serine/threonine kinase 31 (STK31), dishevelled binding antagonist of beta catenin 3 (DACT3), adenosine deaminase RNA specific B1 (ADARB1), sialophorin (SPN), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 3124 (C2orf27A / LINC03124), C-type lectin domain containing 9A (CLEC9A), metallothionein 1F (MT1F), integrin subunit beta like 1 (ITGBL1), dual specificity phosphatase 29 (DUSP27 / DUSP29), RNA, U6 small nuclear 529, pseudogene (RNU6-529P), synaptotagmin 15 (SYT15), transmembrane protein 240 (TMEM240), 3-hydroxyacyl-CoA dehydratase 2 (HACD2), RFPL1 antisense RNA 1 (RFPL1S), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 937 (LINC00937), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 1907 (LINC01907), ITGB2 antisense RNA 1 (ITGB2-AS1), LMCD1 antisense RNA 1 (LMCD1-AS1) and zinc finger protein 883 (ZNF883).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I tabulate the rankings of 2nd order combination of MFAP4 with the above list, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1]. Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t MFAP4 with MFAP4 – > HSPB6 / PROM1

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS MFAP4									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T MFAP4									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
HSPB6 - MFAP4	225	169	290	246	PROM1 - MFAP4	286	346	346	239
ELN - MFAP4	215	377	194	70	LMCD1 - MFAP4	216	324	305	243
ITGA8 - MFAP4	199	352	317	81	ADCYAP1R1 - MFAP4	228	308	205	104
SEMA5B - MFAP4	293	295	231	34	SRPX - MFAP4	191	241	179	387
PCSK1N - MFAP4	246	264	197	76	SLC17A7 - MFAP4	195	228	218	112
SFRP4 - MFAP4	245	330	326	363	CDH23 - MFAP4	230	256	193	50
NRXN2 - MFAP4	200	216	284	98	ST8SIA1 - MFAP4	280	119	361	240
NPR3 - MFAP4	249	391	347	352	PODXL2 - MFAP4	239	240	273	253
SLC30A3 - MFAP4	217	379	216	175	PRG4 - MFAP4	300	233	324	113
TRIM67 - MFAP4	270	326	153	285	PLP1 - MFAP4	214	255	268	157
LAMP5 - MFAP4	285	351	386	392	MASP1 - MFAP4	258	369	281	94
KIF1A - MFAP4	267	315	241	306	PODNL1 - MFAP4	237	348	224	129
SERPINF1 - MFAP4	257	354	254	111	CLEC10A - MFAP4	276	350	323	48
PRPH - MFAP4	320	347	296	278	SCN7A - MFAP4	256	268	298	384
TTC29 - MFAP4	240	342	322	72	THBS1 - MFAP4	329	303	332	282
ITGA11 - MFAP4	209	321	215	36	DUOX1 - MFAP4	243	278	186	260
LHCGR - MFAP4	308	388	340	389	RBP4 - MFAP4	302	378	366	288
DUOX2 - MFAP4	143	364	316	229	FGF7 - MFAP4	347	366	349	376
NKD1 - MFAP4	259	319	280	372	RCN3 - MFAP4	223	282	274	33
NXPH2 - MFAP4	291	392	374	349	RBMS3 - MFAP4	122	234	261	205
BOC - MFAP4	261	327	247	122	CHRN3 - MFAP4	289	340	350	208
DRD2 - MFAP4	274	292	310	151	KCNA6 - MFAP4	297	336	301	353
PID1 - MFAP4	236	258	292	176	PDE1C - MFAP4	282	325	372	333
PPP2R2B - MFAP4	227	371	329	351	S100B - MFAP4	229	286	387	391
COL26A1 - MFAP4	205	309	327	268	FRZB - MFAP4	204	266	201	19
C1QTNF7 - MFAP4	279	250	255	181	RHOBTB3 - MFAP4	309	381	377	390
CA3 - MFAP4	221	356	314	156	SVEP1 - MFAP4	232	254	341	9
HSPA12A - MFAP4	284	252	287	24	PDZRN4 - MFAP4	252	375	370	386
TMEM130 - MFAP4	253	387	379	373	TVP23A - MFAP4	355	329	380	380
LDHD - MFAP4	385	237	302	342	PRRT2 - MFAP4	366	221	233	146
CYP2S1 - MFAP4	334	373	389	327	NT5DC2 - MFAP4	326	273	291	377
FILIP1L - MFAP4	319	262	309	262	RAB31 - MFAP4	349	297	382	310
NPNT - MFAP4	360	344	360	345	ATOH8 - MFAP4	364	383	365	284

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between MFAP4 VS Individual members.

/ ELN / LMCD1 / SLC12A1 / FBLN1 / ITGA8 / ADCYAP1R1 / SEMA5B / SRPX / PCSK1N / SLC17A7 / SFRP4 / CDH23 / NRXN2 / ST8SIA1 / NPR3 / PODXL2 / SLC30A3 / PRG4 / TRIM67 / PLP1 / LAMP5 / MASP1 / KIF1A / PODNL1 / SERPINF1 / CLEC10A / PRPH / SCN7A / TTC29 / THBS1 / ITGA11 / DUOX1 / LHCGR / RBP4 / DUOX2 / FGF7 / NKD1 / RCN3 / NXPH2 / RBMS3 / BOC / CHRN3 / DRD2 / KCNA6 / PID1 / PDE1C / PPP2R2B / S100B / COL26A1 / FRZB / C1QTNF7 / RHOBTB3 / CA3 / SVEP1 / HSPA12A / PDZRN4 / TMEM130 / TVP23A / LDHD / PRRT2 / CYP2S1 / NT5DC2 / FILIP1L / RAB31 / NPNT / ATOH8 / VAMP5 / ARMC4 / CCDC126 / GPR183 / ITGAM / GPR27 / MAP6 / MACROD2 / STARD5 / IL17D / PEAK1 / HEG1 / HOXB2 / CD248 / P2RY14 / YPEL2 / FAM131A / CABP4 / MAMSTR / FZD8 / MYOZ1 / PDE4DIP / CSRNP3 / CIITA / SERTM1 / KCNE1 / NME9 / PLAG1 / EXT1 / BGN / EPHB3 / PYCR1 / NEB / FAM43B / ADRA2C / CSF1 / FLRT2 / PRKG1 / CYP4Z1 / CYP4X1 / RTN4RL2 / C2orf88 / KBTBD12 / STK31 / DACT3 / ADARB1 / SPN / C2orf27A / CLEC9A / MT1F / ITGBL1 / DUSP27 / RNU6-529P / SYT15 / TMEM240 / HACD2 / RFPL1S / LINC00937 / LINC01907 /

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS MFAP4									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T MFAP4									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
VAMP5 - MFAP4	372	177	359	209	ARMC4 - MFAP4	292	279	213	221
CCDC126 - MFAP4	324	380	356	256	GPR183 - MFAP4	392	261	390	338
ITGAM - MFAP4	368	362	342	247	GPR27 - MFAP4	367	219	319	45
MAP6 - MFAP4	340	311	381	271	MACROD2 - MFAP4	363	229	267	340
STAR05 - MFAP4	331	202	300	32	IL17D - MFAP4	341	276	220	311
PEAK1 - MFAP4	359	345	336	283	HEG1 - MFAP4	353	246	250	224
HOXB2 - MFAP4	250	236	343	86	CD248 - MFAP4	332	201	358	123
P2RY14 - MFAP4	351	224	230	84	YPEL2 - MFAP4	391	316	368	297
FAM131A - MFAP4	390	323	369	347	CABP4 - MFAP4	365	203	222	302
MAMSTR - MFAP4	307	355	335	184	FZD8 - MFAP4	374	332	353	234
MYOZ1 - MFAP4	305	312	294	102	PDE4DIP - MFAP4	321	287	320	366
CSRNP3 - MFAP4	356	314	279	361	CIITA - MFAP4	310	181	229	321
SERTM1 - MFAP4	254	13	242	261	KCNE1 - MFAP4	313	337	285	220
NME9 - MFAP4	384	353	339	218	PLAG1 - MFAP4	387	249	337	279
EXT1 - MFAP4	345	335	388	242	BGN - MFAP4	265	231	286	348
EPHB3 - MFAP4	388	147	375	202	PYCR1 - MFAP4	287	199	362	320
NEB - MFAP4	342	334	313	250	FAM43B - MFAP4	344	270	355	281
ADRA2C - MFAP4	271	245	289	139	CSF1 - MFAP4	270	222	376	272
FLRT2 - MFAP4	315	291	338	194	PRKG1 - MFAP4	322	372	344	126
CYP4Z1 - MFAP4	298	358	363	233	CYP4X1 - MFAP4	343	361	384	355
RTN4RL2 - MFAP4	378	386	299	269	C2orf88 - MFAP4	354	365	265	245
KBTBD12 - MFAP4	317	339	227	103	STK31 - MFAP4	339	382	318	226
DACT3 - MFAP4	294	294	371	241	ADARB1 - MFAP4	379	193	297	190
SPN - MFAP4	318	215	367	318	C2orf27A - MFAP4	369	300	354	308
CLEC9A - MFAP4	333	265	352	74	MT1F - MFAP4	328	301	334	178
ITGBL1 - MFAP4	381	376	348	287	DUSP27 - MFAP4	376	333	276	354
RNU6-529P - MFAP4	361	306	373	316	SYT15 - MFAP4	358	180	331	289
TMEM240 - MFAP4	268	243	282	258	HACD2 - MFAP4	330	390	383	249
RFPL1S - MFAP4	389	374	378	331	LINC00937 - MFAP4	336	290	315	298
LINC01907 - MFAP4	362	210	278	148	ITGB2-AS1 - MFAP4	338	235	307	57
LMCD1-AS1 - MFAP4	323	343	321	108	ZNF883 - MFAP4	371	244	325	251

Table 2: 2nd order interaction ranking between MFAP4 VS Individual members.

ITGB2-AS1 / LMCD1-AS1 / ZNF883.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic MFAP4 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of MFAP4-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

Acknowledgements

Special thanks to Mrs. Rita Sinha and Mr. Prabhat Sinha for supporting the author financially, without which this work could not have been made possible.

Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

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UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t MFAP4

HSPB6 / PROM1 / ELN / LMCD1 / SLC12A1 ...

FBLN1 / ITGA8 / ADCYAP1R1 / SEMA5B ...

SRPX / PCSK1N / SLC17A7 / SFRP4 ...

CDH23 / NRXN2 / ST8SIA1 / NPR3 ...

PODXL2 / SLC30A3 / PRG4 / TRIM67 ...

PLP1 / LAMP5 / MASP1 / KIF1A ...

PODNL1 / SERPINF1 / CLEC10A / PRPH ...

SCN7A / TTC29 / THBS1 / ITGA11 ...

DUOX1 / LHCGR / RBP4 / DUOX2 / FGF7 ...

NKD1 / RCN3 / NXPH2 / RBMS3 / BOC ...

CHRN3 / DRD2 / KCNA6 / PID1 / PDE1C ...

PPP2R2B / S100B / COL26A1 / FRZB ...

C1QTNF7 / RHOBTB3 / CA3 / SVEP1 ...

HSPA12A / PDZRN4 / TMEM130 / TVP23A ...

LDHD / PRRT2 / CYP2S1 / NT5DC2 ...

FILIP1L / RAB31 / NPNT / ATOH8 ...

VAMP5 / ARMC4 / CCDC126 / GPR183 ...

ITGAM / GPR27 / MAP6 / MACROD2 ...

STARD5 / IL17D / PEAK1 / HEG1 ...

HOXB2 / CD248 / P2RY14 / YPEL2 ...

FAM131A / CABP4 / MAMSTR / FZD8 ...

MYOZ1 / PDE4DIP / CSRNP3 / CIITA ...

SERTM1 / KCNE1 / NME9 / PLAG1 / EXT1 ...

BGN / EPHB3 / PYCR1 / NEB / FAM43B ...

ADRA2C / CSF1 / FLRT2 / PRKG1 ...

CYP4Z1 / CYP4X1 / RTN4RL2 / C2orf88 ...

KBTBD12 / STK31 / DACT3 / ADARB1 ...

SPN / C2orf27A / CLEC9A / MT1F ...

ITGBL1 / DUSP27 / RNU6-529P / SYT15 ...

TMEM240 / HACD2 / RFPL1S / LINC00937 ...

LINC01907 / ITGB2-AS1 / LMCD1-AS1 / ZNF883 MFAP4

Table 3: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between MFAP4 and Individual members.